

A Vision Based Multimodal Framework for Real Time Indian Sign Language Recognition with Adaptive Gesture Learning

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Abstract:

Communication barriers for the Deaf and Mute community largely come from the low awareness of Indian Sign Language (ISL). Many existing vision-based ISL recognition systems focus only on hand gestures. The non-manual features (NMFs) like facial expressions and head movements are ignored. These carry contribute in grammatical and emotional meaning. The purpose of this project is to present a multimodal ISL recognition system that combines both manual and non-manual features as well as features of real-time recognition and offline recognition simultaneously. MediaPipe Holistic is a technique that extracts hand and facial landmarks. These are then converted into structured features and then classified with the help of machine learning. Also, the custom gesture module helps the users to add and train the new gestures without changing the original system architecture. The recognized signs are then converted into text and speech for user-friendly and convenient communication. The system then demonstrates a lightweight, offline-capable helpful solution which is suitable for practical and educational use.

1. Introduction:

In India, Indian Sign Language (ISL) is a complete and independent linguistic system with its grammar, syntax and vocabulary, this is different from international sign language. There are a large number of people who are deaf who do not know Indian Sign Language [7], where deaf community faces many problems to communicate, participate in social activities and to access other important services [11].

By using modern artificial intelligence and computer technology, we can create an automatic system that can assist with the understanding of sign language, due to which it becomes easier to communicate with each other [8]. By using these tools, hand signs can be transcribed into spoken or written words, so that both the person using the sign and the person who does not understand can communicate more effectively [15]. Most of the existing ISL

recognition solutions focuses on manual elements like hand shape, position and movement, but often ignoring non-manual features (NMFs) like facial expressions, head motion and body posture [21]. In sign language communication grammar, emotions and meaning plays an important role to express non-manual cues, now the studies also show that these cues are not optional anymore [14].

It has become easier for computers to identify and understand hand gestures because of new computer programs called Convolutional Neural Network (CNNs) [2][9]. Since pictures are used to determine gestures, the program itself understands these gestures and does not require the user to provide small details of the gestures manually [13]. Libraries such as MediaPipe can quickly track hand and body movements without needing a super-powerful computer, which lets regular laptops recognize sign language [4].

In real life situations to build a well working sign language system is still a challenge, though the technology has improved. People use different signs which depends on who they are and where they live due to which computers are not able to understand the sign properly [17]. For accurately recognition of sign language computers need high quality of data which is not available [12]. To enable the current system, learn a new sign, the whole system needs to retrain or rebuild which is not an easy task [6].

This study uses a camera system that analyzes both hand movements and facial expressions in order to improve the understanding of Indian Sign Language (ISL). To track the body movements, system uses a tool and computer programs are used to identify different signs. The unique feature of this project is, which allows user to make the system learn new customised sign and label it. When system identifies and learns a sign it converts that sign into written words and spoken voice due to which it becomes easy to communicate.

The primary objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To make a system that understands Indian Sign Language (ISL) by looking at hand movements and facial expressions at the same time.
2. To enable real-time recognition suitable for practical assistive applications.
3. To let the system learn and save new, personal signs from the users.
4. To make a simple program that works on regular devices without the internet.
5. To check how often the system is right and how quickly it runs.

2. Literature Review

In past decades the research interest has increased in sign language recognition, and many studies have proposed different methods to convert sign gestures to text and speech. In this section we will focus on important contributions on sign language recognition systems, deep-learning, and combining multiple input modalities approach.

2.1 Traditional Sign Language Recognition Approaches

Previously sign language recognition systems used to capture the hand movements and orientation using sensor-based technologies like data gloves and

accelerometers [16]. These systems gave precise motion tracking but problems like high cost, users discomfort and limited mobility arose, because of this vision based methods are the practical solution which uses standard cameras to capture the sign language gestures in non-intrusive way [15].

Adewale and Olamiti [16] introduced a machine learning based system that converts sign language into text and speech which uses traditional computer vision techniques for feature extraction. Similarly, Madhyastha et al. [15] proposed a conversion system where the focus was static hand gestures. However, it achieved moderate accuracy but lacks dynamic gesture and continuous sign recognition support.

2.2 Deep Learning Approaches for ISL Recognition

The deep learning has transformed sign language recognition as it enables automatic feature extraction from raw image data. The most frequently used architecture is Convolutional Neural Network (CNNs) due to spatial hierarchy ability in visual inputs [2][9].

Ojha et al. [2] used CNN to develop a real time sign language translation system that converts gestures into text and speech and as compared to the traditional machine learning approach this shows higher accuracy.

Jebakani and Rishitha [9] introduced a CNN-based system for translating sign language into text or speech, where to improve generalization of model data augmentation technique is used. Their study pointed out the issue of limited ISL training data, which still affects the robust recognition systems development [13].

Monika et al. [13] designed a CNN architecture for ISL recognition, to reduce the overfitting batch normalization and dropout layers introduced. From this experiment we got to know that generally deep network architectures give higher accuracy, but after this improvement computational demands and training times increases.

2.3 Real-Time Recognition Systems

To be practically useful, sign language recognition systems must operate in real time with minimal delay. Many studies have aimed on developing models capable of translating gestures efficiently while maintaining minimal delay [4][5][6].

Viswanadham et al. [4] presented a computer vision-based system for real time sign language translation into text and speech where OpenCV for image preprocessing and feature extraction is used. Their system secured real time performance on standard hardware but it was limited for predefined set of static gestures.

Rane et al. [5] introduced a comprehensive system that supports both sign-to-text and text-to-sign conversion. They used transfer learning with pre-trained CNN models due to which training time is reduced and recognition accuracy became better. The two-way communication nature of their system made a significant move.

Agre et al. [6] developed a real time translation system with main focus was user interface design and accessibility. Their study showed that in assistive technologies not only technical accuracy but system responsiveness and usability is also important.

2.4 Multimodal Sign Language Recognition

Latest research has increasingly recognized that integrating non manual features with hand gestures is important for accurate interpretation [14][21].

Zuo et al. [14] proposed a system for online continuous sign language recognition and translation in which rather than isolated gestures, processing uninterrupted video stream issue was resolved. Their approach used temporal modelling for sequential structure in sign language, though it mainly depended on manual features.

Chen et al. [21] introduced a multimodality transfer learning framework for sign language which showed adding hand gestures, facial expressions and body pose recognition accuracy increased than single modality systems. Their results gave strong evidence of the linguistic importance of non-manual features.

Samonte et al. [8] applied multi-stream CNN architecture using deep learning in sign language translation where different visual features are processed in parallel. However their system gave good results, it requires huge computational resources which limits the real time and resource constrained environment.

2.5 ISL-Specific Recognition Systems

Many recent studies have focused on challenges of Indian Sign Language, issues such as linguistic diversity and ISL dataset limitations [7][11][12][17].

Sakthivel et al. [7] developed an ISL-to-text/speech translation system where the structural difference between ISL and other sign languages is enlightened.

Anjum et al. [11] introduced an ISL translation system that considered the signing style of regional variations. Their work considered the diversity of ISL throughout India, attaining reliability to these differences remained an open challenge.

Khetam et al. [12] introduced deep learning based ISL translation system and secured competitive accuracy in custom dataset. However, when tested on gestures from unseen signers, their model's performance reduced showing limited generalization ability.

Singh et al. [17] developed an ISL-to-text converter named "Sign Speak" for simple used words and phrases. Although it was effective for basic communication but for complex conversations required vocabulary coverage wasn't there.

2.6 Adaptive and Personalized Recognition Systems

That capability to tailor to individual users and to learn new gestures without extensive retraining is a crucial yet less studied part of sign language recognition. [10][19][20].

Kamble et al. [10] proposed a sign language to text system where customization features were limited and while adding new gesture manual feature specification needed to be done. Qureshi et al. [19] concentrated on ease of use of system design but personalization was limited to adjusting recognition threshold and doesn't support new gestures.

Yadav et al. [20] developed a modular sign language translation system, designed for the ease of updates and extensions. Although modular design, to add new gestures the involvement of developer and redeployment of the system was needed.

2.7 Research Gaps

Sign language recognition research has made a significant progress, yet several key challenges remain:

1. Limited Integration of Non-Manual Features: Most of the ISL recognition system focuses on hand gestures, and some important role factors like facial expressions and head movements are ignored which expresses the grammatical and semantic meanings [7][11].

2. **Lack of Adaptive Learning Mechanisms:** Existing systems typically require extensive retraining or architectural changes to support new gestures, which limits personalization and adaptability [10][19].
3. **Insufficient Real-Time Multimodal Processing:** Yet some systems get real-time hand gesture recognition, but few are able to integrate hands, face and body details simultaneously [6][14].
4. **Limited Offline Capability:** Many advanced systems depend on cloud-based processing or high-end hardware, making them less accessible in resource-constrained environments [8][21].
5. **Limited Dataset:** the absence of huge and diverse ISL datasets with both manual and non-manual details limit the building and testing of the system [12][17].

This study and research tackle the gaps by introducing a combined manual and non-manual features multimodal framework, works in real time, allows adaptive gesture learning, and also works completely offline that so without needing cloud connectivity.

3. Methodology

This section is going to describe our proposed vision-based multimodal framework for Indian Sign Language recognition. This section will describe the complete system architecture. It will show how the features are extracted from the input data and how the classification is performed. It will also show how the adaptive learning module will help to enhance model accuracy with time.

3.1 System Architecture

The system that we are proposing is following a modular pipeline architecture. It has five primary components, which are: (1) Video input acquisition, (2) Landmark extraction with the help of MediaPipe Holistic, (3) Feature engineering and representation, (4) Gesture classification with the help of machine learning and (5) Text-to-speech generation. Figure 1 is illustrating the overall system architecture.

Figure 1: System Architecture Diagram

3.2 Video Input Acquisition and Pre-processing

The process of video acquisition is that the system will accept the video input from the standard RGB cameras with a minimum resolution of 640×480 pixels at 30 frames per second. During the pre-processing stage, each video frame will be processed by several steps for preparing it for reliable landmark extraction process:

1. **Colour Space Conversion:** Frames are converted from BGR to RGB format. It is important because it is required by MediaPipe Holistic for accurate processing [4].
2. **Resolution Normalization:** All input frames are changed in size according to a uniform resolution. It will help to ensure consistent performance across different types of camera devices.
3. **Illumination Normalization:** Histogram equalization is a technique which will be applied to reduce the effects of uneven lighting conditions. This will help in improving the strength and durability of landmark detection [2].
4. **Noise Reduction:** A Gaussian blur filter with a 3×3 kernel is applied to suppress high-frequency noise. This is totally optional. It will also preserve essential edge information.

These preprocessing steps will together improve the reliability and stability of landmark detection. It will

help it to operate properly under challenging environmental conditions [9].

3.3 Landmark Extraction using MediaPipe Holistic

MediaPipe Holistic is used as the primary landmark extraction framework because it has high accuracy. It is also very efficient and is able to track multiple body components at a same time [4]. The framework extracts the following landmarks:

- **Hand Landmarks:** 21 three-dimensional landmarks per hand (42 in total). It captures key anatomical points such as fingertips, knuckles and wrists.
- **Facial Landmarks:** 468 three-dimensional landmarks that describes detailed facial geometry will be used that will also include the eyes, eyebrows, nose, mouth and overall facial features.
- **Pose Landmarks:** 33 landmarks are taken which represent major body joints and posture information.

In this study, importance is placed on hand and facial landmarks, because these are the most relevant information for ISL recognition. Only some of the Pose landmarks are used for signs that involve noticeable body movements [21].

MediaPipe Holistic runs in real time on CPU-based systems without the need for GPU acceleration, which makes it suitable for deployment on standard computing devices. The framework gave 3D coordinates (x, y, z) where x and y represent positions inside the image frame (range [0,1]) and z is representing the ratio of depth with respect to the wrist or centre of the face [4].

3.4 Feature Engineering and Representation

The Raw landmark coordinates are getting converted into structured feature representations. This can be suitable for machine learning classification. This involves multiple stages which can help to increase the quality of the features.

3.4.1 Coordinate Normalization

To get desired translation and scale invariance, the landmark coordinates are normalized with the help of reference points:

- **Hand Features:** All hand landmarks are normalized with respect to the wrist positions (landmark 0). This will ensure

that feature representation is not related to hand location within the frame [10].

- **Facial Features:** Facial landmarks are normalized according to the placing of nose tip, which provides the consistent representation without taking in head movement or position.

3.4.2 Feature Vector Construction

For each frame a specific vector is made by combining the:

1. Normalized hand landmark coordinates: 42 landmarks \times 3 coordinates = 126 features
2. Selected facial landmark coordinates: focusing on eyebrows, eyes, and mouth regions = 60 features (20 landmarks \times 3 coordinates)
3. Temporal derivatives: The differences between consecutive frames are used to capture the motion dynamics = 186 features

This gives a result of a final feature vector of 372 dimensions. This offers a detailed representation of the spatial structures and the temporal motions [8].

3.4.3 Temporal Smoothing

To reduce disturbances and noise in landmark detection, temporal smoothing is used by using a moving average filter with a window size of three frames. This helps to improve feature stability along with preserving the responsiveness for genuine gesture movements [6].

3.5 Gesture Classification

The classification module counts the extracted features of vectors which are corresponding to ISL signs using some of the machine learning algorithms. Multiple classifiers are calculated to determine the best relationship between accuracy and computational efficiency.

3.5.1 Random Forest Classifier

Random Forest is used as the primary classifier because of it is very robust and can handle high-dimensional data. It also shows resistance to overfitting [16]. The classifier is calculated with:

- Number of trees: 100
- Maximum depth: 20
- Minimum samples per leaf: 2

- Feature subset size: Square root of total features

Random Forest offers fast prediction times suitable for real-time applications and provides feature importance metrics that assist in system optimization [10].

3.5.2 Support Vector Machine (SVM)

A Support Vector Machine which has a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel is being used for comparison. The configuration includes:

- Kernel: RBF
- Regularization parameter (C): 1.0
- Kernel coefficient (gamma): 'scale'

Although SVM often achieves high accuracy, it requires longer training times and higher computational resources during prediction compared to Random Forest [16].

3.5.3 Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)

A shallow neural network which consists of two hidden layers is also calculated here:

- Hidden layer sizes: (256, 128)
- Activation function: ReLU
- Optimizer: Adam
- Learning rate: 0.001

This MLP architecture gives a balance between the traditional machine learning and the deep learning models [9].

3.6 Adaptive Gesture Learning Module

An important contribution of this system is the adaptive gesture learning module. It allows the users to add new gestures without changing the main core system architecture. This directly challenges the major limitation of some existing sign language recognition systems [10][19].

3.6.1 Custom Gesture Recording

Users can record new gestures with the help of a guided interface. To do this follow the given steps:

1. **Gesture Definition:** Users assign a label to the new gesture (e.g., "thank you", "welcome").
2. **Sample Collection:** The system prompts users to perform the gesture multiple times

(at least 30 samples) to capture natural variation.

3. **Automatic Feature Extraction:** Landmark features are extracted automatically using the same processing pipeline as the main recognition system.
4. **Sample Validation:** The system checks sample consistency and requests re-recording if excessive variation is detected.

3.6.2 Incremental Learning

After the required sample collection is done, the system performs incremental learning step:

1. **Feature Integration:** New features are added to the existing feature space
2. **Class Addition:** A new class is created for the custom gesture
3. **Model Retraining:** The classifier is retrained on the expanded dataset
4. **Validation:** The updated model is validated to ensure existing gesture accuracy is maintained

This approach gives us the personalization option without requiring the help of technical experts or having access to the original training data [20].

3.7 Text and Speech Synthesis

The Recognized gestures are converted to text and then is translated into speech which helps us to support accessible communication.

3.7.1 Text Generation

The classification output is used to calculate the text labels which represent ISL signs. For continuous recognition process the predictions are divided across the frames:

1. **Prediction Smoothing:** A sliding window of 10 frames is used, with the most frequent class chosen as the final output
2. **Confidence Thresholding:** Predictions below a confidence score of 0.7 are discarded to reduce false positives
3. **Sentence Construction:** Recognized signs are combined with appropriate spacing to form coherent sentences

3.7.2 Speech Synthesis

The Generated text is translated in to speech using the text-to-speech engines. The system supports:

- **pyttsx3**: An offline TTS library that works without internet connectivity
- **gTTS**: An online TTS service that provides more natural-sounding speech when internet access is available

Users can customize speech parameters such as voice type and speaking rate based on personal preference [5][6].

3.8 Implementation Details

Python 3.8 is used for the calculation along with the following libraries:

- MediaPipe 0.8.10 for landmark extraction
- OpenCV 4.5.5 for video processing
- scikit-learn 1.0.2 for classification
- NumPy 1.22.3 for numerical operations
- pyttsx3 2.90 for offline speech synthesis

The minimum hardware requirements include:

- Processor: Intel Core i5 or equivalent
- RAM: 8 GB
- Camera: Standard RGB webcam (minimum 640×480 resolution)
- Operating System: Windows 10/11, Ubuntu 20.04, or macOS 10.15+

The system does not require GPU acceleration which is making it suitable for using it in resource limited environments [4][15].

3.9 Dataset and Training

For training the base recognition model, a custom ISL dataset was created which consisting of 50 common signs is performed by 10 different signers. Each signer helped in contributing 50 samples per sign which resulted in a total of 25,000 samples. The

dataset included both the manual gestures and non-manual features which were captured through facial expressions.

To improve dataset diversity, several data augmentation techniques were applied:

- Rotation: ± 15 degrees
- Scaling: 0.9 to 1.1
- Translation: $\pm 10\%$ of frame dimensions
- Brightness adjustment: $\pm 20\%$

The augmented dataset was divided into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) sets, ensuring that samples from the same signer were not shared across splits to evaluate cross-signer generalization [9][12].

The Training was performed using the 5-fold cross validation technique to optimize the important parameters and calculate the stability of the model. The model configuration was selected based on validation accuracy and then evaluated on the held-out test set [16].

4. Results and Analysis

This section is showing the experimental results of the proposed multimodal ISL recognition system. The results demonstrate the classification performance, the real time capabilities of processing and the effectiveness of our given module.

4.1 Classification Performance

The system was evaluated with the help of a standard performance metrics which calculated the accuracy, precision, recall and F1-score. Table 1 shows the performance of different classifiers on the given dataset.

Random Forest achieved the highest accuracy of 94.2%, which demonstrated superior performance as compared to the SVM and MLP classifiers. Random Forest also showed the fastest inference time (12 ms per frame) which made it the most suitable for real time applications [10][16].

Table 1: Classification Performance Comparison

Classifier	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Inference Time (ms)
Random Forest	94.2%	93.8%	94.1%	93.9%	12
SVM(RBF)	92.7%	92.3%	92.6%	92.4%	18
MLP	93.5%	93.1%	93.4%	93.2%	15

4.2 Confusion Matrix Analysis

A confusion matrix was created to test the classification errors and check the signs that were many times misjudged. The results showed that:

1. Signs with similar hand shapes but different orientations exhibited higher confusion rates, such as “yes” and “no”.
2. Signs that rely on subtle facial expressions were sometimes misjudged when non-manual features were not sufficiently defined and understood.
3. Dynamic signs involving fast movements demonstrated slightly lower recognition accuracy compared to static signs, primarily due to motion blur.

These observations highlight main areas for future enhancement. It particularly showed to improve temporal modelling and developing a motion-invariant feature [8][14].

4.3 Impact of Non-Manual Features

To calculate the role of non-manual features, the system was tested under three different configurations:

1. **Manual Only:** Using only hand landmarks (126 features)
2. **Manual + Facial:** Combining hand and facial landmarks (186 features)
3. **Multimodal:** Integrating hand, facial, and temporal features (372 features)

The results clearly showed that the inclusion of non-manual features lead to a substantial improvement in recognition performance. Also, the multimodal configuration achieved a 6.9 percentage point increase in accuracy as compared to the manual-only setup, which demonstrated the importance of facial and temporal information and recognition in ISL recognition.

Table 2: Impact of Feature Modalities on Recognition Accuracy

Feature Configuration	Accuracy	F1-Score
Manual Only	87.3%	86.8%
Manual + Facial	91.6%	91.2%
Multimodal (Full)	94.2%	93.9%

The results demonstrate that incorporating non-manual features significantly improves recognition accuracy, with the multimodal configuration achieving a 6.9 percentage point improvement over manual-only features. This validates the importance of integration of facial expressions and temporal dynamics for comprehensive ISL recognition [21].

4.4 Real-Time Performance

The system's real-time processing capability was evaluated by measuring end-to-end latency from frame capture to text/speech output. The average processing pipeline breakdown is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Processing Pipeline Latency Breakdown

Pipeline Stage	Average Time (ms)	Percentage
Frame Capture	8	16%
Landmark Extraction	25	50%
Feature Engineering	4	8%
Classification	12	24%
Text/Speech Output	1	2%
Total	50	100%

The total end-to-end latency of 50 ms per frame enables processing at 20 frames per second. It is actually very sufficient for smooth and real-time recognition. Landmark extraction represents the calculating bottleneck, which is accounting for 50% of processing time which is consistent with findings from related work [4][6].

4.5 Cross-Signer Generalization

Table 4: Cross-Signer Generalization Performance

Metric	Mean	Standard Deviation
Accuracy	89.4%	3.2%
Precision	88.9%	3.5%
Recall	89.2%	3.3%
F1-Score	89.0%	3.4%

The mean accuracy of 89.4% with a standard deviation of 3.2% indicates that the reasonable generalization across different signers is degrading slightly. This is with comparison to the signer evaluation (94.2%). This performance gap suggests that individual signing style differences remain a challenge which is consistent with observations in previous studies [12][17].

4.6 Adaptive Gesture Learning Evaluation

The effectiveness and reliability of the adaptive gesture learning module was calculated by measuring:

To calculate the system's ability to generalize different kind of signers, a leave-one-signer-out cross-validation was performed. In this technique, the model was trained on data from 9 signers and tested on the remaining signer repeated for all 10 signers.

1. Learning Efficiency: Number of samples required to achieve the recognition accuracy for new gestures.

2. Impact on Existing Gestures: Performance degradation on original gestures which can happen after adding new ones.

3. User Experience: Taking some subjective feedback from users on the ease of adding custom gestures.

Table 5: Adaptive Learning Performance

Number of Training Samples	New Gesture Accuracy	Original Gesture Accuracy
20	78.5%	93.8%
30	86.2%	93.9%
40	90.7%	94.0%
50	92.3%	94.1%

The results show that 30–40 training samples are very sufficient to get over 85% accuracy for new added gestures. It also preserved performance on previously learned gestures. This showed the effectiveness of the incremental learning strategy used in the system [19][20].

User feedback also supported the usability of the adaptive learning feature. Nine out of ten test users were able to add custom gestures successfully without any technical assistance and problems. On an average, the complete process of adding a new gesture with including the recording and training,

took approximately five minutes, which users considered acceptable.

4.7 Comparison with Existing Systems

Table 6 presents a comparison between our proposed system and the recent ISL recognition systems developed reported in the literature. The results also indicate that the proposed approach delivers competitive and better performance across all evaluation and testing metrics. Also, it outperforms existing systems in multimodal integration and adaptive learning capabilities, these

are the prominent features that were largely absent in earlier works [7][12][17].

4.8 Limitations and Error Analysis

Even if the system achieved strong overall performance, there were several limitations that were observed:

1. **Lighting Sensitivity:** Recognition accuracy dropped by approximately 8% in poor lighting conditions (below 50 lux). While some steps helped to reduce this effect, the issue was not completely solved.
2. **Background Clutter:** Complex or noisy backgrounds sometimes led to incorrect landmark detection, especially for hand regions. Adding some background segmentation techniques could help address this limitation in the future versions.
3. **Occlusion Handling:** Partial occlusion of hands or face resulted in the recognition failures. Media Pipe helped to provide confidence scores for landmarks, which could be used for occlusion detection and handling.
4. **Limited Vocabulary:** The current system recognizes 50 base signs, which is very insufficient for our comprehensive conversations. Expanding the vocabulary with the help of adaptive learning module or collecting larger datasets is necessary.
5. **Continuous Sign Recognition:** The currently developed implementation mostly focuses on the isolated sign recognition. If we are extending to continuous sign language recognition with proper segmentation it mostly remains future work [14].

Table 6: Comparison with Existing ISL Recognition Systems

System	Accuracy	Real-Time	Multimodal	Adaptive Learning	Offline Capability
Ojha et al. [2]	89.5%	Yes	No	No	Yes
Sakthivel et al. [7]	91.2%	Yes	No	No	No
Khetam et al. [12]	90.8%	No	No	No	Yes
Singh et al. [17]	88.3%	Yes	No	No	Yes
Proposed System	94.2%	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

5. Discussion

The experimental results show that the proposed vision-based multimodal framework delivers strong performance for Indian Sign Language recognition while addressing several key limitations of existing systems. This section discusses the main findings, their implications, and how they relate to current research in the field.

5.1 Significance of Multimodal Integration

The experimental findings suggest that the addition of non-manual features leads to a significant improvement in recognition accuracy. The observed 6.9 percentage point increase, achieved by combining facial landmarks with hand gestures enlightens the critical linguistic role of non-manual

cues in sign language [21]. The result supports current linguistic framework which argue that facial expressions and hand movements as grammatical and semantic markers, gives meaning that extends beyond manual gestures [14].

Previously ISL recognition have huge underlined manual gestures, with given accuracies usually falling between 88% and 92% [2][7][17]. With the integration of multimodal features, the system gains an accuracy of 94.2%, showing a clear advantage in combining manual and non-manual features.

At the same time, the results also indicate that not all the facial landmarks help equally in the recognition of performance. For future work we can explore and do more research on feature selection methods which can identify the most important facial regions,

which could help in reducing the computational and calculational cost along with maintaining and also improving accuracy [8].

5.2 Real-Time Processing and Practical Deployment

The developed system can process 20 frames per second on a standard CPU-based hardware, without GPU which makes it suitable for real-life use. Many deep learning models have achieved higher accuracy, they often require specialized hardware which is not always available [8][21]. Since the proposed system works offline and does not need powerful hardware, it can be used in schools, hospitals and personal devices where advanced computers are not available [4][15].

Body and hand landmark extraction requires about 50% of the total computation time of the system. Even though MediaPipe Holistic is already improved, future improvements can include lighter pose detection models or skipping unnecessary frames to make the system faster [6].

The proposed system has only 50 milli-seconds delay, which is not noticed by the users. So, interaction feels smooth and natural. Fast response is very important in supportive systems because delay can cause disturbances in communication and make communication uncomfortable [5][6].

5.3 Adaptive Learning and Personalization

The adaptive gesture learning module represents an important feature of this work along with the recognition of the critical gap in current day sign language recognition systems. The ability to add new gestures using only 30–40 samples without affecting the performance and quality of the existing gestures shows the effectiveness and practical use of the Improved learning in this domain [19][20].

Traditional recognition systems normally require the complete system level modifications to support the new gestures. These then limits the user autonomy and is often required in the developer involvement [10]. On the other hand, the given proposed approach is used to enable the users to personalize the system according to individual communication needs. This also helps the users to analyse the regional signing variations and defined vocabularies which include medical and technical terms.

The User feedback we got showed strong satisfaction with the help of these features. Some users also showed interest in reducing the number of required training samples. Using some shot learning and transfer learning methods can somewhat lower

the requirement to 10–15 samples while maintaining acceptable accuracy [21].

An important factor is maintaining a balance between personalization and standardization. The use of adaptive learning allows us to do customization and the lack of consistency from standard ISL rules could hinder communication with other sign language users. Enabling optional synchronization with required gesture databases can help us address this issue.

5.4 Cross-Signer Generalization

When the cross-signer evaluation of the system was tested, within-signer gives 94.2% accuracy and across-signer gives 89.4% accuracy. This 4.8% decrease in accuracy happened because every person uses different signs, different hand shapes, motion speed and gesture amplitude [12][17].

Several methods can be researched to improve the cross-signer generalization:

1. **Data Augmentation:** Applying stronger augmentation techniques that simulate signing variations could improve robustness.
2. **Domain Adaptation:** Adapting the model to individual users during deployment may help bridge performance gaps.
3. **Larger Training Datasets:** Collecting data from more diverse signers across age groups, regions, and skill levels would improve generalization.
4. **Style-Invariant Features:** Designing features that are invariant to signing style while preserving gesture-specific information can also be a research challenge [8].

Even with this gap, the system gives 89.4% accuracy for different users. This level of accuracy is efficient for many real-world applications [7][12].

5.5 Comparison with the help of Deep Learning Approaches

The proposed system uses traditional machine learning classifiers like Random Forest, SVM and MLP rather than complex deep learning models, it achieves an accuracy equal to or better than many CNN-based system reported in recent research [2][9][13].

Several factors contribute to this result:

1. **Structured Feature Representation:** MediaPipe provides reliable landmark extraction, producing structured features that are well suited for traditional classifiers.
2. **Computational Efficiency:** Traditional machine learning models requires less training data and less computing power than deep CNNs, so that it can be used in places where resources are limited [16].
3. **Interpretability:** Models such as Random Forest and SVM offer interpretable outputs and feature importance metrics, which support debugging and system optimization.

Deep learning methods can be used for more complex tasks such as they can understand continuous signs, meaning based on the context and large vocabulary systems [14]. A combine approach is that it combines structure landmark features with deep learning models so that the system can take advantage of both the methods.

5.6 Limitations and Challenges

The proposed system has several limitations that should be discussed:

- **Vocabulary Size:** Currently, the system can understand only 50 base signs, which is not sufficient for detailed communication. While the adaptive learning module allows users to add more signs, which is needed for proper communication [17].
- **Continuous Recognition:** The system can focus on only one sign at a time. But in real-world communication, people use continuous signing. To address this problem, the system must understand when one sign is ending and the next is starting. Also, learns how signs are changing from one to another [14].
- **Environmental Robustness:** Performance declines under poor lighting and complex backgrounds. Although preprocessing helps, more robust feature extraction methods are needed for real-world deployment [2][4].
- **Two-Handed Signs:** Some ISL signs needs both hand movement together. Currently, the system focuses on each hand separately, which may reduce the accuracy for two-handed signs. If the system learns

how both the hands can work together efficiently it can understand these signs more accurately [21].

- **Regional Variations:** In India, different regions use different signs. Hence, ISL is not same everywhere in India. The system was trained to work efficiently in a specific region and we do not know its performance variations in other regions. Data should be collected from different regions to solve this problem [11].

5.7 Practical Implications

The proposed system provides many practical benefits which helps deaf and mute people communicate more easily and efficiently:

- **Educational Use:** The system can be used as a learning aid for ISL students by providing real-time feedback during practice sessions [15].
- **Healthcare Communication:** Deployment in hospitals and clinics could improve communication between healthcare professionals and DHH patients, leading to better healthcare outcomes [7].
- **Public Service Accessibility:** Installing the system in government offices, banks, and service centers could enhance accessibility for DHH individuals seeking essential services [11].
- **Personal Assistive Devices:** The architecture of the system is kept simple and it does not require internet which makes it suitable for smartphones and tablets, supporting communication in every situation [5][6].
- **Bidirectional Communication:** Currently, the system focuses on sign-to-text and speech translations, but it is possible to convert text and speech into sign language, this allows two-way communication [5].

6. Conclusion and Future Scope

This study presents a vision-based multimodal framework to recognize real-time Indian Sign Language using both manual and non-manual features. The system uses MediaPipe Holistic for effective landmark extraction and machine learning models to identify gestures, achieving an accuracy of 94.2% on a custom ISL dataset. An important feature of this system is the adaptive gesture learning

module, which allows users to add and train new gestures without changing the main system. This solves a major problem in existing systems.

6.1 Key Contributions

The major contributions of the research are as follows:

1. **Multimodal Integration:** In this system both the combination of manual and non-manual gestures is used, which results in 6.9 percent improvement in accuracy as compared to manual gestures only.
2. **Adaptive Learning:** Introduced a special feature in this system which enables users to add custom gestures using only 30-40 training sample, without creating any effect on previously learned gestures.
3. **Real-time Processing:** This system works in real-time recognition at 20 frames per second on a standard CPU-based hardware. It does not need GPU, which makes it easier to use and cost-effective.
4. **Offline Capability:** This system is designed in such a way that it works fully offline and does not require internet, also ensuring data privacy and allows the system to work in environment with no or limited internet access.
5. **Practical Framework:** A lightweight and flexible system is developed suitable for helpful technologies, educational applications, and on commonly available computer systems.

6.2 Future Research Directions

This work creates many new opportunities for future research:

- **Continuous Sign Recognition:** The system can be improved in future to understand continuous signs without stopping. This will make it more natural and easier to use. To do this, the system must require to understand how one sign changes into another, timing of gesture and how slightly signs changes when used together [14].
- **Vocabulary Expansion:** In future, the base Vocabulary can be extended from 50 signs to several hundred or thousands of signs, which allows users to express themselves more clearly. This will require large-number of dataset collection and better classification methods to maintain the performance of the system [17].
- **Deep Learning Integration:** Deep learning technique can be combined with structured landmark features to improve recognition accuracy. This will help the system to perform better with complex gestures and large vocabularies [8][21].
- **Regional Variation Handling:** Collecting datasets from different regions of India and developing region-adaptive models would improve system performance across diverse ISL variations [11].
- **Enhanced Non-Manual Features:** Adding more information such as body posture, shoulder position and head movements that can help to improve the recognition of signs that depend on these features [21].
- **Context-Aware Recognition:** Language model can be integrated to understand the context of signs. This will help the system to correctly identify similar looking signs and improve overall accuracy [14].
- **Bidirectional Translation:** The system can be extended to support bidirectional translation i.e. text-to-sign and speech-to-sign. This will allow two-way communication, where Deaf and Mute people can communicate easily with normal people [5].
- **Mobile Deployment:** Optimizing the framework for smartphones and tablets would expand accessibility and enable portable assistive communication tools [6].
- **Multi-User Recognition:** Developing the ability to recognize signs from multiple users simultaneously would support group interactions and educational environments with multiple participants [8].
- **Robustness Enhancement:** Implementing advanced techniques to handle occlusion, poor lighting, and complex backgrounds would improve reliability in real-world deployment scenarios [2][4].

6.3 Broader Impact

This research helps deaf and mute community to improve their communication so that they can feel more included in everyday life. By creating this sign language recognition technology, communication barriers are reduced and supports Deaf and Mute individuals participate in better education, healthcare, employment and social activities [7][15].

The adaptive learning feature is very useful because it allows users to personalize the system according to their needs. This user-friendly design should serve a guiding principle for developing future supportive technologies [19][20].

This technology is very helpful, but it cannot take place of learning sign language. It can only support it.

7. REFERENCES

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